

TERRITORIAL DIFFERENCES IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH DIALECTS

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Abstract: Studying and classifying dialects within languages makes easier to learn. It is easier and more effective when each language is studied in its own way. This thesis deals with dialect units in Uzbek and English and their differentiation.

Keywords: dialect, language, linguistics, pronunciation, literature, feature.

Introduction

It is known that each language has its own dialect units. The problem of distinguishing dialectal units in one language from another is awaiting its solution. Because languages are a social phenomenon, they undergo different changes in each region. That is why special dialects within languages have emerged and continue to do so. However, it is also interesting to distinguish the dialects of the two languages.

The term dialect in dialectological literature means dialect are also used. Nowadays, it means a general linguistic dialect used. The term dialect is derived from the Greek word. Prof. V.V.Reshetov he actively used the term in his research in the sense of a group of dialects. The term refers to the scientific and scientific methodology of the subject in Russian also found in the literature. [1]

Dialectology is one of the basic terms of dialectology in general. The term Uzbek dialectology is the name of a science that studies Uzbek dialects. The object of study of dialectology, in particular, Uzbek dialectology, is the local dialects and dialects of the Uzbek language. Identification of new cases in lexical, morphological, syntactic features without change. Based on this main goal, the following tasks should be performed in practice:

1. Describe the phonetic, morphological, syntactic, lexical features of individual dialects, groups of dialects and dialects.
2. The role of dialects in the emergence and development of the national language, to determine the dialects that form the basis of the national language.
3. Determining the relationship between dialects, literary language and sister languages based on dialect materials.
4. Determining the distribution of Uzbek dialects on the basis of similar features.
5. Classify dialects by identifying common linguistic features and compiling diagrams of the distribution of dialects in a given area. [3]

The study of dialects provides rich and valuable material for both the history of language and the history of the people. The lexical elements and some grammatical forms of the literary language, which have disappeared and changed, may have been preserved in the local dialects. Therefore, dialectology is very important for the study of the history of language. The unknown features of ancient Turkic written monuments can be identified and supplemented

by studying the phonetic, lexical, morphological, lexical-morphological features of modern Uzbek dialects on a scientific basis.

Sheva (dialect, accent) (Persian: قارات قارق قارت و قاتا تو قارات) the smallest regional form of a language with its phonetic, grammatical, and lexical features is used.

There is one side of the dialect that is called linguistic geography. Linguistic geography (lingo-geography) is the study of linguistics is a branch of linguistics that is widespread in a particular territory (sounds, forms of the morphemes, words) indicates the attitude towards the place. Regional features related to the history of the people and the history of the language by means of comparative explanations. Linguistic geophysics studies both territorial dialects. One of its most important features is fiction, which has a certain language. Map and atlas area means of expressing linguistic geography, the main purpose of which is to explain the laws and years of language development, the emergence of specific dialects and their relationship to the national language.

Linguistic geography is a series of general linguistic problems, that is, if a language has a dialect, it must address issues such as how their features are limited, the approach of dialects to the national language, and so on.

Examples of Uzbek dialects are: (in Uzbek regions)

qorinja (chumoli -ant), goz (yong'oq-nut), karvich (g'isht-brick) – Khorezm;

norbon (narvon-ladder), bodrak (varrak-kite), poku (ustara-shaver) – Bukhara;

mishiq (mushuk-cat) - Fergana;

inak (sigir-cow), morcha (chumoli-ant), pishak (mushuk-cat) - Samarkand.

Some words in dialect may also be in literary language. But they have different meanings. For example, the word "bowl" means "cup" in Khorezm, in the literary language it means "a container for liquid food", the word "lagan" means "a bowl for washing dishes", in the literary language it means "a container for roast food".[2]

Dialects in English also have their own history. English is actually an unusual language. Already a blend of early Frisian and Saxon, it absorbed Danish and Norman French, and later added many Latin and Greek technical terms. In the US, Canada, Hawaii, Australia, New Zealand, South Africa, and elsewhere, it absorbed terms for indigenous plants, animals, foodstuffs, clothing, housing, and other items from native and immigrant languages. Plus, the various dialects, from Cockney to Jamaican, and innumerable sources of slang, from Polari to hip hop, continue to add novel terms and expressions to the mix. Pronunciation (for our purposes):

i: as in beet

æ as in bat

a: as in father

ü as in German

ö as in French

kh as in Scottish loch (lokh)

gh as in Dutch

ñ as in Spanish

Southern English engages in r-dropping, that is, r's are not pronounced after vowels, unless followed by another vowel. Instead, vowels are lengthened or have an /r/ off-glide, so fire becomes /fai'r/, far becomes /fa:r/, and so on.

regular use of "broad a" (/ɑ:/), where GA (General American) would use /æ/.

"long o" is pronounced /'u/, where GA uses /ou/.

final unstressed i is pronounced /i/, where GA uses /i:).

The English of well-bred Londoners, especially graduates of the public schools (e.g. Eton and Harrow) and "Oxbridge" universities, was the origin of "the Queen's English," also known as Received Pronunciation (RP), BBC, or "posh."

Types of British Accents

Cockney - this is one of the UK's most famous dialects, and it goes hand in hand with London. It came about as the dialect of the London working classes, especially in the poorer East End of the city. The Cockney dialect also gave us Rhyming Slang, and you can still hear plenty of market traders round the East End shouting out in Cockney from their stalls. With the Cockney accent there are lots of 'glottal stops', and the 'th' sound frequently changes to an 'f' sound.

Estuary English- here's another dialect that is London-based. The 'Estuary' in question is the Thames Estuary, and this dialect is spoken by people who live along its stretch. It's now becoming one of the most widely spoken accents down south. It's not as posh as RP, but it's not as 'common' as Cockney

Yorkshire - it is a big county in England, and lots of people speak with a variation of the Yorkshire dialect as a result. Known as 'God's Own County', Yorkshire has a delicious dialect. One of the biggest difference between this dialect and RP is that words ending in an 'ee' sound, like 'nasty', are pronounced with an 'eh' sound, like 'nasteh'.

Northern Irish - the Northern Irish accent is quite a beautiful one, and a strong one too. The first thing you'll probably notice about Northern Irish is how many letters seem to be missing from words when people speak it. For example, 'Northern Irish' would be pronounced more like 'Nor'n Ir'sh'!

Scottish - the Scottish dialect varies hugely from city to city, town to town, and becomes increasingly like the Irish accent in the Western Isles, and increasingly like Nordic languages in the islands to the far north. The more remote the area, the stronger the accent seems to become, so people from the Shetland Islands can be hard to understand at first

Brummie - If somebody come from Birmingham, he or she will speak the Brummie dialect - like Ozzy Osbourne. He may have been living in LA for years, but he hasn't lost his accent - which goes to show just how strong this dialect is. It's quite soft, and elastic, and lumpy sounding.

Scouse - the Liverpoolian accent is one of the most famous British regional accents and it's a very nasal dialect that can be hard to copy at first.

Geordie - people from Newcastle speak the Geordie dialect, and they're called Geordies too. One of the biggest differences between Geordie and RP is that the 'r's at the end of words aren't pronounced, and tend to be pronounced as 'ah' instead. So a word like 'sugar' becomes 'sug-ah'. And a word like, say, 'Space Centre' becomes 'Space Cent-ah'. [4]

In addition here are more examples,

An American might pronounce the word, "hello," by speaking the "h" sound.

A Brit might pronounce the word, "hello," without speaking the "h" sound.

A Northern American might say, "hello."

A Southern American might say, "howdy."

Someone from the East Coast might say, "What's poppin'?"

A Southern American would understand this, but would probably never say it.

Someone from the South might say, "How'r y'll?"

A Northeastern American would understand this, but probably never say it.

In a nutshell, a dialect is a type of language spoken by a particular region or group of people and differs in the historical literature and regions of each nation. Dialect is a broader and deeper concept than language. Most dialects have only specific accents, but they are more than just pronunciation differences. Although the differences between the dialects of Uzbek and English are as diverse as the history and origins of the two languages, it helps for modern learners to distinguish languages within regions.

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